

Servant Leadership and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment as Mediation: A study at 'X' Hospital, Jakarta

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Keywords

Abstract

Servant Leadership;

Organizational Culture;

Organizational Commitment;

Employee Performance;

This study aims to determine and analyze the effect of servant leadership and organizational culture on employees through organizational commitment as mediation. This study uses a causal quantitative approach, which explains the effect of servant leadership variables and organizational culture variables on workforce variables. The results of this study indicate that: (1) There is a positive and significant direct effect of servant leadership on organizational commitment, (2) There is a positive and significant direct effect of organizational culture on organizational commitment, (3) There is a positive and significant direct effect of organizational commitment on employee performance, (4) There is a positive and significant direct effect of servant leadership on employee performance, (5) There is no positive and significant direct effect of organizational culture on employee performance. (6) There is a significant and positive effect of servant leadership on employee performance through organizational commitment with partial mediation at the structural level, and (7) There is a significant and positive effect of organizational culture on employee performance through organizational commitment with full mediation at the structural level.

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1. Introduction

An organization of any type and form certainly has a goal and wants to achieve it. At present, which has entered the industrial era 4.0, with the use of information technology, changes and developments have accelerated. In order to compete and maintain and align with the goals of an organization, human resources play a very important role than other organizational resources. The success of an organization is largely determined by human resources (Dessler, 2017). In the health industry, direct health services to the community are required to provide fast, precise, and accurate services. It does not turn a blind eye that businesses in the health sector are currently increasingly competing and competing with each other to improve the best service. One of the organizations in the health sector is a hospital. A hospital is a form of integrated health facility that provides good, quality, and complete services (Purnami, 2017).

Health services provided are with service patterns that can improve health status and reduce morbidity and mortality. The hospital is also a service organization with capital-intensive, complex human resources, knowledge-intensive, and technology-intensive (Khotimah, 2021). The human resources in the hospital consist of various professionals with health and non-health workers. The health workers consist of specialists, general practitioners, nurses, nutritionists, pharmacists, laboratory assistants, and pharmacists. Therefore, good service from a hospital is very much determined by its human resources, especially the health workers who deal directly with individual patients. While the infrastructure and medical devices used following the era of technological sophistication are required to be able to use them.

The increasing number of currently operating hospitals cannot be separated from the competition between hospitals in providing the best and integrated health services and accommodating referral patients. The number of hospitals in Central Jakarta is currently 41 hospitals, with 19 Type B hospitals. This means that almost 50% is dominated by this type of hospital, and competition will be created. Hospital 'X,' the author will study, is Type B, located in Central Jakarta.

Table 1. List of Central Jakarta Type Hospitals

No.	Hospital Name
1.	RSAL dr. MintoHarjo
2.	hospital Aesthetics Development
3.	hospital Dharma Jaya
4.	hospital Dharma Sakti
5.	hospital Husada
6.	hospital Islamic Jakarta
7.	Jakarta Eye Center Hospital, Menteng
8.	Kramat Lima Hospital
9.	hospital Kramat 128
10.	hospital Kemayoran Family Partners
11.	hospital Pure Teguh Sudirman
12.	hospital PGI Cikini
13.	hospital Primaya Evasari
14.	hospital Proclamation
15.	hospital RE. Martadinata
16.	hospital St. Carolus
17.	hospital Yarsi Jakarta
18.	RSIA Budi Kemuliaan

19.	RSIA YPK Mandiri
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Data Processed by Researchers 2022

Since the operation of the 'X' Hospital began on July 24, 2019, where 'X' Hospital is still relatively new, it has been operating for approximately 4 (four) years. In its second year of travel in 2020, it is known that Indonesia is facing the Covid-19 pandemic where the health services provided by the hospital are focused on Covid patients. So, providing other health services is limited, as well as 'X' Hospital, which is one of the places to serve Covid patients. So it has quite an impact on the performance of the hospital. The same thing happened on his journey into the third year of 2021. Covid is getting worse. So that it has an impact on the performance of the hospital from the time it starts operating. Performance appraisal of the hospital, according to (Rahimi & Kavosi, 2014) said to be good by considering several aspects of performance, namely the average length of stay, number of beds, nosocomial infection rate, and patient satisfaction. These aspect indicators are included in the performance measurement of 'X' Hospital using the Balance Score Card (BSC). The following are the performance achievements of 'X' Hospital starting operations:

Table 1. Hospital Performance Achievements 'X'

NO.	YEAR	ACHIEVEMENTS
1.	2020	< 70%
2.	2021	>70%
3.	2022	>70%

Source: Interview with the Director of 'X' Hospital

Based on Table 2. the performance of 'X' Hospital in 2020 is less than 70%. As for performance gains in 2021, the achievement will be above 70%, and in 2022, it will still be with the same achievement in the sense that it is still below the set target of 100%. This data was obtained from an interview with one of the directors of 'X' Hospital. Some of the results of interviews with several employees and after making observations at 'X' Hospital. The above conditions, with the results of the hospital's performance, illustrate that the leader's role is very large to lead and motivate his team to achieve goals. Leadership is key for a company or organization in providing direction, planning, and training (Blackwell, 2009). That the key to leadership is setting direction, as well as aligning people towards it, and motivating as well as inspiring. Because the hospital is a business in the service sector that prioritizes helping sick people, leadership is needed to serve according (Smith et al., 2004). Servant leadership is more effective in non-profit, voluntary, or religious organizational settings. In this case, according to (Muller & Smith, 2018), servant leadership also impacts several performances: financial, customer, internal process, learning, and innovation based on the Balanced Score Card (BSC).

In addition, what affects performance is the existence of discipline, one of which is participation in training and employees who are present on time when they enter working hours. From the results of the sources obtained through interviews and observations, punctual attendance at entering working hours has not been achieved, namely still below 100%, and many employees still arrive late. As for employee participation in mandatory training, it is still far below the target set according to one source from the head of the training and education section, namely:

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Table 2. Participation of Training Participants

NO.	YEAR	TRAINING PARTICIPANTS
1	2020	0 %
2	2021	40 %
3	2022	60%

Source: 'X' Hospital Training Section, 2023

In 2020, 0% of training will be abolished due to the focus on services for Covid cases which is currently highly known from the above data that the participation of employees in mandatory training (mandatory training) is still far from the target of all employees. This requires the role of leaders to grow and provide awareness to employees of the importance of developing individual employees in fulfilling competence, knowledge and improving employee performance to achieve organizational goals.

Many factors can improve performance to achieve success in achieving the vision and mission of an organization because performance is a picture of the level of achievement or implementation of a program. One of the factors is organizational commitment. According to Malik (2010), organizational commitment is an individual's relative strength and involvement in an organization. The employees in the hospital, both medical and non-medical, have their attitudes shown in the form of their loyalty to achieving the hospital's goals. In line with that, according to (Hartaroe et al., 2021), This loyalty is manifested by the large number of nurses who have worked in hospitals for tens of years and are able to become hospital marketers at the same time.

The Vision of 'X' Hospital is to make the hospital based on Islam with high-quality health services and international standards. In realizing this vision, stewardship is needed in carrying out its mission with a leader who can invite, care about his team and prioritize his followers' interests above his own (Greenleaf, 2008).

In the medical industry, in this case, hospitals pay great attention to the name of safety, both for patients and employees, to avoid accidents or wrong drug administration. Therefore in this industry, safety culture is very important. The performance of health workers cannot be separated from what is called patient safety. According to (Nivalinda et al., 2013), the application of patient safety culture carried out by nurses reflects the performance behavior of nurses who are influenced by the leadership of the head of the room. And according to (Rayatin, 2018), nurse performance is an indicator of the quality of a hospital. Where the task of a nurse is to provide nursing care, and the manager or head nurse plays a central role in carrying out care. The results of the patient safety culture survey obtained from the Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture (HSOPSC) instrument were 131 respondents with the following results:

Table 4. Patient Safety Culture

NO.	PART	RESULTS (%)
1.	Work unit	50,6
2.	Manager / Head of Section / Head of Division / SPV / Ka. Installation	40,31
3.	Communication	45,94
4.	Frequency	30,84
5.	Safety Level in the Unit	50,7

6.	Hospital	50.01
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Source: processed by the September 2022 Quality Team

From the data above, it can be concluded that there is still a great need for leadership to invite, direct and motivate employees to achieve patient safety in service. One of the leader's roles is to direct and solve existing problems to achieve good performance. According to Peter F. Drucker (Pabundu Tika, 2014), Organizational Culture is the subject of solving external and internal problems whose implementation is carried out consistently by a group which is then passed on to its new members as the right way to understand and think and feel about these problems. According to (Pedrosa et al., 2021), organizational culture is defined as a set of shared mental models that reflect group life, namely how to see the world, solve problems, react emotionally to what is perceived, and value things. Thus, organizational culture plays a strategic role in improving the effectiveness of organizational performance in dealing with and solving problems.

Apart from servant leadership and organizational culture, organizational commitment is also a factor that can improve employee performance. According to Malik (2010), organizational commitment is an individual's relative strength and involvement in an organization. A company's performance is determined by its employees' attitude of commitment, which is inseparable from the role of the leader who controls and inculcates a mutually agreed-upon organizational culture. Therefore, the factors that affect performance include servant leadership (Kamanjaya et al., 2017), organizational culture (Nikpour, 2017), and organizational commitment.

The researcher conducted a pre-survey to strengthen this study by distributing questionnaires by random sampling of 16 (sixteen) employees consisting of medical and non-medical employees at 'X' Tpe B Hospital, using a Likert scale filled out via Google form with the following results.

Table 3. April 2022 'X' Hospital Pre-survey results

NO.	DIMENSIONS	FREQUENCY					Total score	IDEAL SCORE	RESULTS	STANDARD (%)
		SS (5)	S(4)	R(3)	TS (2)	STS (1)				
1	<i>Servant Leadership</i>	12	34	22	32	8	338	80	62.5	100
2	Organizational culture	9	21	17	15	2	212	80	66,25	100
3	Organizational Commitment	5	15	21	7	0	162	80	67.5	100
4	Performance	14	29	12	6	3	237	80	74.0625	100
Total Average Score									67.5781	100

Source: Processed data (2022)

Table 5 data. From the results of the pre-survey, it can be seen that with the standards set, 100% has not been achieved. With the achievement of an average score of 67.57%. The author's reason for distributing the questionnaire above is to represent which variables affect the performance of 'X' Hospital employees. Based on previous research (Kamanjaya et al., 2017) stated that servant leadership had no significant effect on employee performance. This means that the better the servant

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leadership, there is the tendency to increase employee performance. However, servant leadership positively and significantly influences employee organizational commitment. These results indicate that the behavior of leaders who instill service as the priority emphasizing improving service to others and subordinates as an approach to subordinates at work, introducing a sense of togetherness with subordinates, and being able to share when making an organizational decision, will increase subordinates' organizational commitment.

Research conducted (Howladar & Rahman, 2021) states that servant leadership directly influences organizational commitment and organizational behavior, and organizational commitment directly impacts organizational citizenship behavior. It also reveals that the relationship between servant leadership and organizational commitment is partly mediated by organizational commitment. While research conducted (Nurmala & Jasin, 2021) shows the influence of organizational culture on employee performance. And the influence of organizational culture on organizational commitment, and organizational commitment acts as an influence of organizational culture on employee performance. In addition, research (Ekhsan & Aziz, 2021) shows that servant leadership influences employee performance & organizational commitment, and organizational commitment influences employee performance (Muchsinati & Mea, 2022).

Based on the background and research that has been done previously by several researchers, the authors intend to conduct research related to the influence of Servant Leadership (X1) and Organizational Culture (X2) as independent variables on employee performance (Y) as the dependent variable with organizational commitment (Z) as an intervening variable in the study of 'X' Jakarta Hospital. This hospital has never done this research before because Hospital 'X' has not been operational for a long time.

2. Research Methods

This study uses analytical methods, which include descriptive statistical analysis and nonparametric statistical analysis. This research is quantitative research for data analysis by using data which is descriptive statistics by describing and describing the collected data as it is without intending to make generally accepted conclusions). Data analysis techniques are used to show a tool that is measured to what extent the tool measures what is being measured. A questionnaire is valid if the questions can reveal something that is measured by the questionnaire.

3. Results and Discussion

Hypothesis test

Table 6. Hypothesis testing

	Path Coefficient	P values	95% Path Coefficient Confidence Interval		f square
			Lower limit	Upper limit	
H1. Servant Leadership -> Organizational Commitment	0.411	0.000	0.264	0.546	0.191

H2. Organizational culture -> Organizational Commitment	0.395	0.000	0.252	0.547	0.177
H3. Servant Leadership -> Employee Performance	0.318	0.000	0.141	0.489	0.070
H4. Organizational culture -> Employee Performance	0.070	0.540	0.139	0.311	0.003
H5. Organizational commitment -> Employee Performance	0.299	0.001	0.099	0.474	0.065

Data sources processed by researchers (2023)

Based on Table 6. the results of testing the hypothesis above it is known as follows;

The influence of servant leadership on organizational commitment

Accepted that there is a significant influence of servant leadership on organizational commitment with path coefficient (0.411) and p-value (0.000 <0.05). Every improvement in servant leadership will increase organizational commitment. Within the 95% confidence interval, the influence of organizational commitment in improving employee performance is between 0.264 and 0.546. Nevertheless, the existence of servant leadership in organizational commitment has a moderate effect at the structural level (square = 0.191). The need for continuous application of servant leadership, which is considered very important when there are changes in organizational rules, the application of servant leadership organizational commitment will increase to 0.547.

The influence of organizational culture on organizational commitment

Accepted that there is a significant influence on organizational culture and organizational commitment with path coefficient (0.395) and p-value (0.000 <0.05). Any changes to the organizational culture will increase organizational commitment. Within the 95% confidence interval, the influence of organizational commitment in improving employee performance lies between 0.252 and 0.547. Even so, the existence of organizational culture in organizational commitment has a moderate effect at the structural level (f square = 0.177). The need for continuous application of organizational culture is considered very important when there are rules or policies in implementing organizational culture, so organizational commitment will increase to 0.547.

The influence of servant leadership on employee performance

Accepted that there is a significant influence of servant leadership on employee performance with path coefficient (0.318) and p-value (0.000 <0.05). Every improvement in servant leadership will increase organizational commitment. Within the 95% confidence interval, the influence of

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organizational commitment in improving employee performance lies between 0.141 and 0.489. Even so, the existence of servant leadership on employee performance has a moderate effect at the structural level (f square = 0.070).

The influence of organizational culture on employee performance

Not accepted, that is, there is no significant influence of organizational culture on employee performance with path coefficient (0.070) and p-value (0.540 > 0.05). Every time the organizational culture is strengthened, there is a decrease in employee performance. Within the 95% confidence interval, the influence of employee performance on decreasing employee performance lies between 0.139 and 0.311. Nevertheless, the existence of organizational culture on employee performance has a moderate effect at the structural level (f square = 0.003), almost close to the low structural level of 0.002. There is still a need to apply organizational culture, which is considered important when there are new habits in developing work culture; employee performance will increase to 0.311.

The effect of organizational commitment on employee performance

Significant influence received there is a significant influence of organizational commitment on employee performance with a path coefficient (0.070) and p-value (0.000 < 0.05). Any change in organizational commitment will increase organizational commitment. Within the 95% confidence interval, the influence of organizational commitment in improving employee performance lies between 0.099 and 0.474. Even so, organizational commitment to employee performance has a moderate effect at the structural level (f square = 0.065). The need to strengthen organizational commitment, considered important when there is a sense of remaining in the organization, will increase employee performance to 0.474.

Indirect Effect

Test mediating intervening roles of variables using mediation analysis procedures that refer to references. The table below is the result of indirect influence.

Table 7. Indirect effect (*Indirect Effect*)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Servant Leadership (X1) -> Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.123	0.121	0.042	2,929	0.003
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Organizational Commitment (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.118	0.120	0.046	2,569	0.010

Source: Data processed using Smart PLS 4 (2023)

Based on Table 7 above and based on the path coefficient statistical analysis, then;

Servant leadership on employee performance through organizational commitment

Organizational commitment is a significant mediating variable mediating the indirect effect of servant leadership on employee performance, with a path coefficient of 0.123 and a p-value of 0.003 < 0.05. Because the servant leader variable significantly affects employee performance, and organizational commitment significantly mediates, the role of organizational commitment is partial mediation (Complementary et al.). Thus it was concluded that the sixth hypothesis in this study was accepted.

Organizational culture on employee performance through organizational commitment

Organizational commitment has a significant effect as a mediating variable that mediates the indirect effect of organizational culture on employee performance with a path coefficient of 0.118 and a p-value of 0.010 > 0.05. Because organizational culture has no significant effect on employee performance and significant organizational commitment mediates, the role of organizational commitment is full mediation. Thus it can be concluded that hypothesis seven in this study is accepted.

Discussion

The Direct Effect of Servant Leadership on Organizational Commitment

Based on the path coefficient statistical analysis results, it shows that the value of the original sample was 0.411 in servant leadership on organizational commitment. Other results are also shown in the t statistic of 5.653 and a p-value of 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that the servant leadership variable significantly directly affects the organizational commitment variable. Thus it can be concluded that the first hypothesis in this study is accepted. This result is also in agreement.

The results of this study's hypothesis testing were strengthened by the results of descriptive statistics on the servant leadership variable and the organizational commitment variable, which showed that the average value of respondents' answers was in the medium and good categories, namely the total average servant leadership was 2.84 and organizational commitment was 3.58. The average value shows that most respondents at hospital 'X' agreed on both variables. Some respondents feel the impact of the application of servant leadership where the tendency to prioritize the interests of others above their interests. Most agree with applying ethical principles to achieve success. Leadership that can serve and meet its employees' needs by showing ethical values of good behavior by being humble and sincere. Successful leaders provide exemplary examples to employees so that loyalty fosters organizational commitment in every employee. Leaders can provide exemplary examples in accordance with Sharia behavior and ethical principles in achieving success to make employees loyal and aware of the sense of obligation to stay or be in this organization. This also applies to research researched by (Bellamy, 2021) at a health science education academy, which showed that practicing servant leadership behavior positively affects employee dedication and influences the success and effectiveness of the company.

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Direct Effect of Organizational Culture on Organizational Commitment

Based on the results of the path coefficient, statistical analysis shows that the value of the original sample is 0.395 in organizational culture toward organizational commitment. Other results are also shown in the t statistic of 5.203 and a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05), which means that the organizational culture variable significantly positively affects the organizational commitment variable. Thus it can be concluded that the second hypothesis in this study is accepted. It is also following the results carried out by (Azizollah et al., 2015) that there is a positive relationship between organizational culture and organizational commitment and that organizational improvement and growth have an effect on increasing affective commitment in an organization.

The results of the research hypothesis test were also strengthened by the results of descriptive statistics on work culture variables and organizational commitment variables, which showed that the average value of respondents' answers was in a good category, namely, the total average of organizational culture was 3.55, and organizational commitment was 3.58. The average value shows that the majority of respondents at 'X' hospital answered that they agreed on these two variables; hospital respondents agreed that there were clear work procedures, as well as work coordination between teams, so employees were reluctant to move to another company because a strong collaboration had been formed. Both among employees, both within their work units and between units. The freedom to innovate in the organization allows employees to express all their abilities, and this freedom allows employees to work and spend the rest of their careers with this organization.

The Direct Influence of Servant Leadership on Employee Performance

Based on the path coefficient statistical analysis results, it shows that the value of the original sample was 0.318 in servant leadership on employee performance. Other results are also shown in the t statistic of 3.644 and a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05), which means that the servant leadership variable has a significant direct effect on employee performance variables. Thus it can be concluded that the third hypothesis in this study is accepted.

The results of this study's hypothesis testing are reinforced by the results of descriptive statistics on servant leadership and employee performance variables, which show that the average value of respondents' answers is in the medium and good categories, namely, the total average servant leadership is 2.84, and employee performance is 3.99. The average value shows that most respondents at hospital 'X' agreed on both variables. Respondents partially agreed with a sense of pride in doing the given tasks and were encouraged to do extra or more. As well as in expressing what is thought without any obstacles. The application of the servant leadership model helps employees to be able to listen to all complaints, including in terms of work, making employees happy with the work they are given. Leaders who have a sense of empathy want to listen to employees' complaints so that employees dare to express opinions and are happy to be given a job that will make a good performance.

Direct Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

The path coefficient statistical analysis results show that the original sample's value is 0.070 in organizational culture on employee performance. Other results are also shown in the t statistic of 0.613 and a p-value of 0.540 (> 0.05), which means that the organizational culture variable does not significantly positively affect employee performance variables. Thus it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis in this study is not accepted. These results align with research conducted by

Harwiki (2016) that there is no significant direct relationship between organizational culture and employee performance. The discussion is that there is an inconsistency in the application of organizational culture to employees of women cooperatives in East Java.

The results of the research hypothesis test are strengthened by the descriptive statistical results on work culture variables and employee performance variables which show that the average value of respondents' answers is in a good category, namely, the total average of organizational culture is 3.55, and employee performance is 3.99. The average value shows that most respondents at the 'X' hospital answered that they agreed but were comparable to the respondents' neutral or mediocre responses. Hospital respondent 'X' does not yet have a sense of competition in working to achieve success, so in achieving results or achievements that are not optimal. Achieving maximum results or achievements requires a sense of competition or competition. The lack of competition and competition against employees for success makes work a mundane routine, so achieving employee performance is also normal and has not achieved satisfactory results.

The Direct Effect of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance

Based on the results of the path coefficient, statistical analysis shows that the value of the original sample is 0.299 on organizational commitment to employee performance. Other results are also shown in the t statistic of 3.192 and a p-value of 0.001 (<0.05), which means that the variable organizational commitment has a significant direct effect on employee performance variables. Thus it can be concluded that the fifth hypothesis in this study is accepted. The results of the research hypothesis test are strengthened by the results of descriptive statistics on the variables of organizational commitment and employee performance, which show that the average value of respondents' answers is in a good category, namely, the total average organizational commitment is 3.58, and employee performance is 3.99. The average value shows that most respondents at the 'X' hospital mostly agree with the involvement of employees in effective work planning and contributing to the achievement of hospital goals that make employees want to stay and have a career in the hospital. The strong commitment of hospital employees will improve the performance of 'X' hospital employees. Employee involvement in effective work planning and contributing to achieving hospital goals makes employees feel that they want to continue their careers and be in this organization.

Indirect Influence of Servant Leadership on Employee Performance through Mediation of Organizational Commitment

Based on the results of the path coefficient, statistical analysis shows that the value of the original sample was 0.123 on the servant leadership variable on employee performance with commitment as a mediator between them. Other results are also shown in the t statistic of 2.929 and a p-value of 0.003 (<0.05), which means that the servant leadership variable has a significant indirect effect on employee performance variables with organizational commitment as a mediator. Because the servant leadership variable significantly affects employee performance and organizational commitment significantly mediates, the role of organizational commitment is partial mediation. Thus it can be concluded that the sixth hypothesis in this study is accepted.

The results of the hypothesis testing are reinforced by the descriptive statistical results on the variable servant leadership, organizational commitment, and employee performance as indicated by the answers of the majority of respondents agreeing on these three variables, with the average value

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of the respondents' answers being at the total average value (servant leadership 2.84, organizational commitment 3.58 and on employee performance 3.99). Respondents' perceptions in this study that the leadership skills of the servant leadership model in instilling and cultivating a sense of organizational commitment can increase high employee performance.

The results of testing the H1 hypothesis and testing the H5 hypothesis strengthen the hypothesis test that there is a significant positive influence between servant leadership and organizational commitment. There is also a significant positive influence between organizational commitment and employee performance. It can be concluded that the results of statistical research on servant leadership significantly positively affect employee performance when mediated through organizational commitment.

Indirect Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Mediation of Organizational Commitment

Based on the results of the path coefficient, statistical analysis shows that the value of the original sample is 0.118 in the organizational culture variable on employee performance with commitment as a mediator between them. Other results are also shown in the t statistic of 2.569 and a p-value of 0.010 (> 0.05), which means that the organizational culture variable significantly indirectly affects employee performance variables with organizational commitment as a mediator. Because organizational culture does not significantly affect employee performance, significant organizational commitment mediates the role of organizational commitment *full mediation*. Thus, it can be concluded that the seventh hypothesis in this study is accepted.

The results of the hypothesis testing are reinforced by the descriptive statistical results on the variables of organizational culture, organizational commitment, and employee performance, as shown by the answers the majority of respondents agree on these three variables, with the average value of the respondents' answers being at the total average score (organizational culture 3.55, organizational commitment 3.58 and on employee performance 3.99). Respondents' perceptions in this study that applying organizational culture in instilling and cultivating a sense of organizational commitment may not necessarily improve employee performance.

The results of testing the H2 hypothesis and testing the H5 hypothesis strengthen the hypothesis test that there is a significant positive influence between organizational culture and organizational commitment. There is also a significant positive influence between organizational commitment and employee performance. It can be concluded that statistical research on organizational culture has a significant positive effect on employee performance when mediated through organizational commitment.

4. Conclusion

Following the research that has been done and the discussion regarding the Influence of Servant Leadership and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance Through Organizational Commitment as Mediation: A Study at 'X' Jakarta Hospital, the researchers obtained the following conclusions:

1. *Servant leadership* has a positive and significant direct effect on organizational commitment at 'X' Hospital Jakarta. This means that better applying the servant leadership model will continuously increase organizational commitment.

2. Organizational culture has a significant and positive direct influence on organizational commitment. The stronger the implementation of organizational culture at 'X' hospital, the more organizational commitment will increase.
3. *Servant leadership* has a positive direct effect on employee performance, meaning that the higher the application of the servant leadership model at 'X' hospital will improve employee performance.
4. Organizational culture has no significant direct effect on employee performance at 'X' hospital. This means it is necessary to strengthen organizational culture to increase employee performance.
5. There is a positive and significant direct effect of organizational commitment on the performance of 'X' hospital employees, in the sense that the higher the organizational commitment, the employee performance will increase.
6. *Servant leadership* significantly indirectly affects employee performance through 'X' hospital organizational commitment. The more applied servant leadership fosters a high sense of organizational commitment, it will improve employee performance, so the successful implementation of servant leadership and organizational commitment will improve employee performance.
7. Organizational culture significantly and positively affects employee performance through organizational commitment to 'X' hospital. The stronger the application of organizational culture, the higher organizational commitment will impact employee performance.

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